

Exploring plant cell co-cultivation as a driver of bacterial biosynthetic gene cluster activation and evolution. New

Version 1

Description

The plan has been created to describe data management of the project lzp-2025/1-0098 Exploring plant cell co-cultivation as a driver of bacterial biosynthetic gene cluster activation and evolution.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Exploring plant cell co-cultivation as a driver of bacterial biosynthetic gene cluster activation and evolution.

Researchers

Anete Boroduske (orcid:0000-0003-0077-9811)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Exploring plant cell co-cultivation as a driver of bacterial biosynthetic gene cluster activation and evolution. New

Description:

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Boroduske Anete (anete.boroduske@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Exploring plant cell co-cultivation as a driver of bacterial biosynthetic gene cluster activation and evolution.

Project:

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2029-01-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

pFlux backbone sequence

Plasmid pFlux will be used as a backbone vector for establishing reporter tagged promoter library of *Streptomyces coelicolor* biosynthetic genes. Data describe sequence of the pFlux plasmid.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of plasmid sequencing is to get a reliable information about plasmid sequence that can be applied for plasmid engineering - to build a promoter library.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

Fasta

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

12

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

yes, but it was not possible to find pFlux sequence on plasmid sequence databases

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Streptomyces researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

plasmid sequence is a simple data source that does not need any additional data to be used or understood

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/18933389>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

any txt reading program - like notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anete Boroduske (orcid: [0000-0003-0077-9811](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0077-9811))

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

no security required

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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